

Levels of Anxiety and Depression among Mothers of Children with Intellectual Disability: A Study in the Indian Context

E.V. Johny^{1*}, S. Padmasundari and M.L. Charan³

ABSTRACT

Intellectual disability is a term used when a person has certain limitations in cognitive functioning and skills, which remains throughout the individual's life. Intellectually disabled individuals may fail to deal with complex socio-cultural phenomenon, as a result of which they have traditionally been stigmatized, isolated and deprived of society's resources. This leads to the parents, especially mothers, being more prone to develop anxiety and depression in the long run. This study aimed at finding out whether there is a risk of psychological problems among mothers based on the degree of intellectual disability. Purposive sampling method was adopted and a total of 80 mothers having child with intellectual disability from a varied socioeconomic background consented to participate in this study. The participants were measured on anxiety and depression inventories. The results showed that when the degree of intellectual disability in the child progressed, the mother's risk for depression increased, particularly there were significant differences observed in depression levels of mothers of children with mild intellectual disability and profound intellectual disability. There was no significant relationship was found intellectual disability and anxiety. The findings of the study were discussed in the light of Indian context.

Keywords: Anxiety, Depression, Intellectual Disability, Maternal Anxiety, Maternal Depression.

INTRODUCTION

Intellectual disability (ID) is a type of disability characterized by individuals having significant impairment in both intellectual functioning and socio-adaptive behaviour, which remains throughout the individual's life (Beighton and Wills, 2017). This significant impairment is characterized as performance that is 2 or more standard deviations below the mean based on normed, individually administered standardized tests of cognitive and adaptive function. The diagnosis and classification indexes for ID are based on the specific range of Intelligence Quotient (IQ) scored by individuals, that is, mild (IQ 55–69), moderate (IQ 35–49), severe (IQ 20–34) and profound (IQ <20). As per the reports by the Decennial Population Census of India 2011, 26.8 million individuals are falling under the spectrum of disability, of which 6 percent are intellectually disabled, with a higher prevalence among males (American Association of Intellectual and Developmental Disabilities, 2021). Meanwhile, a later study carried out in India has reported a prevalence rate of 10.5/1000, where the urban population have slightly higher rates than the rural setting. Having the largest population of children with risk of developmental disabilities among the world, ID has evolved as a major health and societal concern in India (Azeem et al., 2012; Bourke-Taylor et al., 2010; Dabrowska and Pisula, 2010).

Intellectually disabled individuals may fail to deal with complex socio-cultural phenomenon, characterized by difficulty in complying with the cultural values required and intellectual and social behavior. As a result, they have traditionally been stigmatized, isolated and deprived of society's resources. Parents and the immediate family members are the main source of support for a child with

ID in any culture. Functional impairment of the child with ID, may be it physical, psychological or social, needs to be compensated for by the caregivers. Thus, parenting a child with ID can bring in outcomes such as increased family closeness, personal growth and joy, which are beneficial and constructive (Hastings et al., 2002; Hastings and Taunt, 2002; Keskin et al., 2010; Kim, 2017). On the downside, having a child with disability not only affects the child functionally, but it is also a concern to the whole family due to the mental and financial burden, and raising a child with disability will be quite challenging for the family as it requires additional time and attention than their typically developed counterparts (Durkin, 2002). Moreover, depending on the severity of the condition, the responsibilities could vary disproportionately. Due to this, parents undergo a lot of distress, worry about their children's future, and experience mental imbalance and psychological confusion while upbringing their children with ID (Emerson, 2003). As a consequence, it makes the parents more prone to develop depression and anxiety in the long run (Lakhan et al., 2015).

Depression is linked to a variety of negative effects limited to not only the individual's cognition, behavior and affect but also poor physical health, lack of self-care and limited social functioning, which in turn affects the quality of care to the children from the parental side (Emerson, 2003; Hastings and Taunt, 2002; Majumdar et al., 2005). Although sparse research evidence exists on anxiety among parents of children with ID, it was found that parents of child with ID scored high on trait anxiety (Maulik and Harbour, 2010). The main reasons for these emerging parental problems cited in the literature are permanency of the condition, disapproval of the child's behavior

^{1,3} Department of Clinical Psychology, National Institute for Empowerment of Persons with Multiple Disabilities (NIEPMD), Chennai, India

² Department of Psychology, Government Arts and Science College Coimbatore, India

*Corresponding Author: EV Johny, Email: - drjohnyev@gmail.com

demonstrated by the society and family members, and insufficient professional support (Mumford et al., 1997).

The coping styles of parents of children with these disabling conditions were extensively researched. In an Indian study that examined the psychological parameters and coping styles of caregivers of ID and psychiatric illness, Panicker and Ramesh (2018) reported that symptoms of stress, anxiety and depression in caregivers were higher in those with children with ID than with psychiatric illness. The most common coping style used by caregivers was religious coping. Dabrowska and Pisula (2010) found difference in social diversion coping among mothers of children with autism and healthy controls. In addition, it was also found that emotion-oriented coping was the predictor of parental stress in parents of children with autism and Down syndrome, and task-oriented coping was the predictor of parental stress in the sample of parents of typically developing children.

In an economically developing nation like India, there are only limited research data available on the effects of upbringing children with ID and risk of psychopathology such as anxiety and depression especially in mothers since they are the primary caregiver. Hence, in our study, the primary objective was to discover the relationship between anxiety, depression, and ID and how the severity of ID in children could contribute to the risk of psychopathology among mothers.

METHODS

Recruitment of the Samples

The inclusion criterion of this study was mothers aged 40 years or below with one intellectually disabled child who is aged less than 18 years. Mothers of children with ID along with other comorbid conditions, mothers who were facing distress by death of any first relative, mothers who are facing distress by any major physical illness which has a disabling nature and mothers who are undergoing treatment for any psychiatric illness were excluded from the study. Participants fulfilling the proposed criteria were first determined, and a total of 147 mothers whose children were diagnosed and availing treatment from the outpatient service clinic at a tertiary care disability rehabilitation centre were purposively approached.

Participants

A group of a total 80 mothers of children with ID expressed their consent to participate. Their mean IQ (see Table 2) was found to be 43.1±14.66. The male mean IQ of 44 and female mean IQ of 41. Of the total sample, 39 percent constituted the mild ID group, 38 percent constituted the moderate ID group, 15 per cent constituted the severe ID group and 8 percent constituted the profound ID group. The mean male age of the children was 10.2 years and the mean female age of the children were found to be 11.5 years.

Procedure

The purpose of the study was explained to participants; written informed consent was taken from the participants who expressed willingness to volunteer, and consequently

the data were collected individually from each participant. The interviewers were clinicians who were trained in the administration of the questionnaires. This study was conducted in accordance with local legal and ethical regulations concerning scientific research.

Table 1: Sociodemographic characteristics.

Variables	Mean (SD)	N
Age (children)	10.69 (3.18)	80
Gender		
Males	–	53
Females	–	27
Age (mother)	33 (5.63)	80
Educational qualification (mother)		
Primary School Education	–	9
Secondary School Education	–	26
Higher secondary Education	–	31
Graduate	–	11
Postgraduate	–	3
Domicile		
Urban	–	69
Rural	–	11
Socioeconomic Status		
Low	–	53
Middle	–	23
High	–	4
Family type		
Joint	–	28
Nuclear	–	52

Table 2: Descriptive statistics for IQ, BDI and BAI scores

Variables	Mean (SD)	N
Depression (BDI)	22.95 (9.06)	80
Anxiety (BAI)	10.65 (6.50)	80
Intellectual Quotient (IQ)		
Male Children	44 (14.81)	53
Female Children	41.14 (14.4)	27
Both Gender	43.1 (14.66)	80

Measures

The participants' basic details and characteristics were collected using a brief sociodemographic questionnaire.

Child Measures:

The children of the mother's included in the study were assessed using either one of the following intellectual functioning assessments (given below) by a clinician, and the IQ were estimated based on the following assessments.

1. Seguin Form Board (SFB; Seguin 1907) was used to measure overall intellectual functioning in children

ranging in age from 3.5 to 10. The test comprises of ten geometrical wooden blocks and a form board, sometimes known as a pegboard, on which the blocks can be properly put. Although it is primarily intended to assess children's form perception and motor coordination, it can also be used to assess IQ in children in the age group above. It has good reliability and concurrent, predictive validity if it's used only in the above-mentioned age groups.

2. Malin's Intelligence Scale for Indian Children (MISIC; Malin A. J. 1969) was used to measure intelligence in children from the ages of 6 to 15 years 11 months. This test comprised of 11 subtests divided into two groups, Verbal and Performance. Verbal Scale consists of 6 subtests and Performance Scale consists of 5 subtests. The test-retest reliability for MISIC was found to be 0.91 for full-scale IQ. MISIC has established concurrent as well as congruent validity.

Maternal Measures:

The following tools were used on the mother's who participated in the study:

1. Beck's Depression Inventory (BDI-II; Beck 1996) was used to measure the depression symptoms among the participants. The BDI-II contains 21 items and it is scored on a 4-point scale from 0 (symptom absent) to 3 (severe symptoms). The test-retest reliability of this scale was found to be $r = .93$ (suggesting robustness against daily variations in mood) and an internal consistency score of $\alpha = .91$. This tool also found to be having good content and criterion validity.
2. Beck's Anxiety Inventory (BAI-II; Beck et al., 1988) was used to measure the anxiety symptoms among the participants. The BAI consists of 21 self-reported items (four-point scale) used to assess the intensity of physical and cognitive anxiety symptoms during the past week. The BAI is psychometrically sound. Internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha) ranges from .92 to .94 for adults and test-retest (one week interval) reliability is .75. Concurrent validity with the Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale, revised is .51; .58 for the State and .47 for the Trait subscales of the State-Trait Anxiety Inventory. The BAI has also been shown to possess acceptable reliability and convergent and discriminant validity for both 14-18 year and inpatients and outpatients.

Data Analyses

The distributions of the study variables were explored using Shapiro-Wilk test statistic, the results of which was non-significant for BDI scores and significant for BAI and IQ scores. It was interpreted that BDI scores were normally distributed but whereas BAI and IQ scores were not normally distributed, hence non-parametric analyses were considered for the study. Spearman correlation was computed for the BAI, BDI and IQ scores to understand the degree of the relationship. Followed by this Mann-Whitney U test was performed to understand the differences in the depression and anxiety levels based on the children gender

and Kruskal-Wallis H test was done to understand the differences in the mother's anxiety and depression level based on the severity of the child's intellectual disability. Post-hoc testing was performed using Tukey's HSD for BDI scores and Intellectual Disability severity, as the BDI scores did not violate the parametric one-way ANOVA assumptions.

RESULTS

The descriptive analysis (Table 1) for the socio-demographic variables of the participants and study variables indicated that the mean age of the mothers who participated in the study was found to be 33 ± 5.63 years, majority of them (39%) had a higher secondary school education, was from an urban (86%), low socio-economic status (66%) and a nuclear (65%) family type. The mean maternal depression and anxiety scores was found to be 22.95 ± 9.06 and 10.65 ± 6.50 . The correlational analysis (Table 3) revealed a significant negative correlative between the IQ scores and BDI scores ($r = -.336, p < 0.01$), and positive correlation between BAI scores and BDI scores ($r = .451, p < 0.01$) of mothers with ID child. Regression analysis could not be computed, as the data violated the assumptions hence effect size was computed for significant correlations from the analysis (i.e., between IQ and BDI scores) to understand the correlational strength, the analysis revealed that medium size of effect with a total variance of 9% explained by the variable.

Table 3: Spearman correlation test statistics for IQ, BDI and BAI scores.

Variables	Depression (BDI)	Anxiety (BAI)	IQ
Depression (BDI)	-		
Anxiety (BAI)	.451**	-	
IQ	-.336**	-.218	-

** Correlation was significant at 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Table 4: Mann-Whitney test statistic for BDI, BAI scores and gender of the children.

Variables	Gender (Children)	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	Mann-Whitney U	Sig.
Depression (BDI)	Males	40.71	2157.50	704.5	.911
	Females	40.09	1082.50		
Anxiety (BAI)	Males	40.71	2157.50	704.5	.911
	Females	40.09	1082.50		

The mean value observed for maternal depression when they had male child was 22.92 ± 9.03 and in the case of female child the mean value was found to be 23 ± 9.30 . The mean value observed for maternal anxiety when they had male child was 10.67 ± 6.18 and for the female child 10.59 ± 7.22 . The Mann-Whitney analysis (Table 3) showed no

significant differences between the child gender and the maternal anxiety ($U = 704.5, p > 0.05$), depression ($U = 704.5, p > 0.05$) levels.

Kruskal-Wallis H statistic revealed that there were significant differences in the maternal depression levels and the severity of the intellectual disability i.e., mild, moderate, severe and profound groups ($H = 11.451, p < 0.01$) but not for maternal anxiety levels.

Table 5: Kruskal-Wallis H test statistic for BDI, BAI scores and gender of the children.

Variables	Intellectual Disability Severity	Mean Rank	Kruskal-Wallis H	Sig.
Depression (BDI)	Mild	30.58	11.541	.01
	Moderate	44.20		
	Severe	46.29		
	Profound	58.64		
Anxiety (BAI)	Mild	36.74	5.340	.149
	Moderate	38.37		
	Severe	54.21		
	Profound	42.79		

Post-hoc testing was performed based on Tukey HSD, the findings indicated that there were significant differences in the maternal depression levels when they had a child with mild and moderate severity of intellectual disability with an observed mean difference of -6.06 between these two groups (i.e., mild and moderate ID). Also, we found that there were significant differences in the maternal depression levels when the mothers had a child with mild and profound severity of intellectual disability with an observed mean difference of -9.84 between these two groups (i.e., mild and profound ID).

DISCUSSION

This study aimed at finding out whether there is a risk of psychological problems among mothers based on the degree of ID. A total of 80 mothers were selected through the purposive sampling method.

From the results obtained, it was evident that when the degree of ID in the child progressed, the mother’s risk for depression significantly increased. This result was consistent with the previous findings based on studies conducted in other cultures (Olsson and Hwang, 2001; Osborn, 2001; Panicker and Ramesh, 2018). Although we did not find any significant differences in depression and anxiety among mothers of male and female children, Nagarkar et al. (2014) in their study found depression was higher among mothers of female intellectually disabled children as they are considered a social burden in an Indian scenario.

Research works in the past have highlighted that parenting a child with ID could be stressful and challenging (Durkin, 2002). It could be due to the reason that in response to

heightened stress, mothers of children with mental retardation often demonstrate increased depression and anxiety compared to mothers of children without mental retardation. This is because of the circumstance that in every Indian household, mothers are expected to assume a greater responsibility to manage the child’s needs and daily household chores. While taking direct care of a child with disability, the responsibilities could demand more time and energy, which consequently brings down their interests in pursuing leisure and social activities.

We cannot hold up the assertion that mothers are the only victim to mental health deterioration while raising a child with ID. In a study based on Pakistani samples, fathers scored higher on anxiety and lower on depression than mothers. Despite the fact that fathers had lower depression rates, the rates were seemingly higher than men in the general population. Depression and anxiety involve various symptomatology such as excessive worry and fear, agitation, poor sleep hygiene, persistent sadness, negative evaluation of oneself, lack of motivation and suicidal tendencies, which makes it difficult for the individuals to carry out daily routines. Hence, it is imperative that parents and caregivers should seek solutions to maintain their mental health to deliver excellent care to their children with disability.

CONCLUSION

The study’s findings indicated high rates of depression among mothers when the child’s degree of ID is very high. Mental healthcare workers and institutions have to be mindful about the issues and should follow an early intervention approach to screen mothers who are at risk of developing psychiatric morbidity.

The management of ID should shift therapeutic and rehabilitation intervention from the individual level to the family level, particularly towards mothers as they are the primary carers. Intervention plans such as recommendation for the carers to consult with experts frequently for treatment, therapy and counselling which would help them to improve their mental health, and teaching them the effective strategies to deal with the child’s behaviour and also enhance appropriate coping skills to deal with the situation should be implemented wherever deemed necessary. Future studies should be done to evaluate the effectiveness of such interventions. Also, the findings of this study must be considered while policy-making and providing aids and financial support so that the parents of children with ID would be benefitted.

LIMITATION

The study had relatively a smaller sample size and was limited to one geographical site in India. There was no balancing of sample size between the different degrees of ID group. It did not include both the parents, and it lacked a control group. Future studies should approach the same issue by carefully considering the limitations of this study.

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